

line transplanting, one pellet every four hills (15 × 20 cm). Quantities of gliricidia green leaves (containing 2.7% N oven-dried basis) to supply 0, 1, 1.5, 2, and 2.5 t green manure/ha were spread uniformly over freshly puddled soil before line transplanting. Karjat-184 was transplanted (3-wk-old seedlings) 7 Jul and harvested 12 Oct.

Deep-placed USG significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). Deep-placed USG at 38 kg N/ha plus green manure increased grain yield more than split-applied PU. □

Effect of USG and PU with limited gliricidia green manure on rainfed transplanted rice yield. ^a Maharashtra, India, 1988 wet season.

Urea N (kg/ha)	Treatment		Yield (t/ha)		Tillers/hill (no.)
	Green manure t/ha	kg N/ha	Grain	Straw	
0	0	0	2.8 c	3.1 d	7.9 e
38 (PU)	0	0	3.0 c	3.2 d	9.7 de
38 (PU)	1	6.3	2.9 c	3.4 d	12.5 abc
38 (PU)	1.5	9.5	2.9 c	3.2 d	10.3 cde
38 (PU)	2	12.6	3.2 bc	3.8 cd	11.1 bcd
38 (PU)	2.5	15.8	3.5 b	4.5 bc	11.9 bcd
38 (USG)	0	0	3.8 ab	4.7 bc	13.0 ab
38 (USG)	1	6.3	3.9 a	5.1 ab	13.5 ab
38 (USG)	1.5	9.5	4.0 a	5.7 a	12.5 abc
38 (USG)	2	12.6	4.2 a	5.5 ab	14.6 a
38 (USG)	2.5	15.8	3.9 a	5.2 ab	15.1 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Integrated nutrient management in irrigated rice

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We studied the integrated effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on growth and grain yield of rice variety GR11 during 1987 wet season. Eight fertilizer combinations were tested (see table).

The test soil was sandy loam with a pH of 7.3, EC 3.5 dS/m, 0.065% total N, 68.5 kg available P/ha, and 332.8 kg available K/ha.

P and K were applied basally; N as ammonium sulfate was applied in four equal splits; basal and at tillering, panicle initiation, and dough stage.

Azolla was inoculated at 1 t/ha 10 d after transplanting (DT). Because of an erratic rainy season, water was not impounded and azolla grew very poorly. The azolla mat was incorporated 30 DT.

Sesbania aculeata was incorporated 1 d before transplanting.

Before incorporation azolla had 2.8% N, 0.48% P, and 3.2% K; *S. aculeata* had 2.5% N, 0.64% P, and 1.0% K.

Delayed planting due to failure of the monsoon and use of brackish irrigation water from a bore well decreased yields.

Grain yield with *S. aculeata* + 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha and *S. aculeata* + 0-20-20 kg NPK/ha were significantly higher than all other treatments except 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha alone and *S. aculeata* + azolla + 0-20-20 kg NPK/ha. □

Effect on rice yield of N applied during reproductive phase

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In the subtropical climate of north India, rice grown with recommended best N split (1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 1 wk before panicle initiation) or standard split (2/3 basal, 1/3 1 wk before panicle initiation) has luxuriant vegetative growth but the canopy turns light green during ripening. We tested supplying a larger proportion of N during reproductive stages (1 wk before panicle initiation, at booting, and at heading), at 120 and 180 kg N/ha. The field experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications in wet season 1988 at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° 29' E, 244 m).

Soil was silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g soil, 0.1% total N, 13.9 kg available P/ha (Olsen), and 202 kg available K/ha (NH₄OAc extraction).

Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was sown 1 Jun and transplanted 5 Jul with basal application of 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha.

Effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on yield and panicles/m². Nawagam, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Biomass (t/ha) incorporated
Control	0.8	108	—
0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	0.8	128	—
40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	2.0	196	—
Azolla + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	1.0	119	3.2
Azolla + 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	1.9	171	1.8
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	3.3	307	26.4
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	3.7	300	22.7
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + azolla + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	2.8	240	24.9
80-17.6-33.2 kg NPK/ha	3.1	258	+1.5
LSD (0.05)	1.1	75	—